

SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLAN IMPLEMENTATION IN BANGSAMORO AUTONOMOUS REGION (BARMM): A PREDICTIVE- CORRELATIONAL APPROACH

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School Improvement Plan Implementation in Bangsamoro Autonomous Region (BARMM): A Predictive-Correlational Approach

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Abstract

Effective school management plays a crucial role in enhancing educational outcomes, particularly in regions facing unique socio-economic and cultural challenges. This study examines the management process in implementing the School Improvement Plan (SIP) among public elementary schools in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Grounded in Henry Fayol's Management Theory, the study explores key management functions—planning, organizing, controlling, activating, implementing, and monitoring—and their impact on school improvement outcomes. Using a predictive-correlational research design, data were collected from 281 respondents, including school heads and teachers, across 18 central public elementary schools in four divisions of BARMM. The findings revealed that all management functions were practised, with monitoring being the most emphasized. The study also found that SIP outcomes were generally achieved, particularly in instructional delivery and student learning development, though challenges remained in instructional resource development, particularly in technology access and infrastructure. Pearson correlation analysis indicated a strong positive relationship between school management processes and SIP outcomes, with monitoring emerging as the strongest predictor of success. The study underscores the importance of efficient management strategies in achieving school improvement goals. To ensure the sustainability of school improvement efforts, it recommends increased funding for instructional resources, capacity-building initiatives for school leaders, and enhanced stakeholder collaboration. By addressing identified gaps and leveraging effective management practices, educational institutions in BARMM can further improve student performance and overall school development.

Keywords: *management process, school improvement plan, resource development, instructional delivery, educational leadership, monitoring strategies*

Introduction

The management process is one of the techniques used by school administrators to run and control an organization and optimize the set goals (Bagine, 2022). This process consists of planning, organizing, controlling, activating, implementing, and monitoring, which are integrated into the school improvement plans (Wanjala, 2021).

All over the world, the management of schools is considered the foundation of quality service delivery. Planning a school improvement plan is vital in attaining learning outcomes for students. However, many school heads lack the needed management abilities in the overall operation of schools (Gamala & Marpa, 2022). A large number of schools had difficulties in management process application to ensure the school improvement plans were implemented.

In the Philippines, the harmonization of the management process in School Improvement Plan development is geared towards a collaborative and transparent system that can promote good governance in school operations (Duterte, 2023). The objective of this strategy is to ensure that students' performance outcomes improve. However, school improvement plan outcome reveals a decline in students learning outcomes as reports of the 2019 Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics revealed that only 10 percent of the country's Grade 5 learners achieved the minimum proficiency at the end of primary education (Devanadera & Ching, 2023). The low-performance outcome is related to the challenges in the implementation and monitoring process.

Based on DepEd Order No. 44 series of 2015, also known as the Guidelines on the Enhanced School Improvement Planning (SIP) process and the School Report Card (SRC), a school can implement certain interventions with the assistance of the community and other stakeholders, following the guidelines outlined in the School Improvement Plan. The expanded SIP preparation process is outlined in the SIP manual. Members of the school's LACs should be involved in the planning and execution of any school improvement projects that tackle issues with the teaching-learning processes.

The Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao received the lowest rating on the report. The intensified effort of the MBHTE has improved the students' performance outcomes. However, Iqbal (2023) mentioned that there is still a long way to attain the said objective. The intensification of a collaborative approach in the management process of the School Improvement Plan is one of the strategies developed by the ministry to ensure good governance of the education services to the Bangsamoro Region.

The difficulties in the management process, such as poor data analysis, support from stakeholders, lack of clear goals or objectives, and insufficient allocation of resources, may hinder the development and can be detrimental to the learning outcome of learners. Therefore, the researcher deemed that the investigation of the management process and School Improvement Plan outcome among the schools in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) can provide evidenced-based data to develop

strategies to help achieve the performance outcome desired.

Research Questions

The study aimed to describe the management process for implementing the School Improvement Plan among public elementary schools in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following research questions.

1. To what extent is the management process implementation of the school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1. planning;
 - 1.2. organizing;
 - 1.3. controlling;
 - 1.4. activating;
 - 1.5. implementation; and
 - 1.6. monitoring?
2. To what extent is the School Improvement Plan outcome achieved in terms of:
 - 2.1. improved instructional delivery;
 - 2.2. instructional resource development; and
 - 2.3. students learning development?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the management processes in the implementation of the School Improvement Plan outcome?
4. Which management processes of the school heads best predict the implementation of the school improvement plan outcome?

Literature Review

Management Process Implementation

The management process in education administration is a key factor in determining a country's education service quality; it is intended to develop quality people who are capable of competing in global competencies, being responsible, and anticipating the future. The school is an educational institution that was founded to develop a more educated human resource, and the quality of a nation is supposed to improve as a result of the existence of schools (Hartati et al., 2018). The management process adopted by the school heads in planning the school improvement programs can boost the planning, organizing, controlling and activating strategies (Lekhetho, 2021).

The school head management process adopted to improve the learning environment is the set of relationships that occur among members of a school community that is determined by structural, personal, and functional factors of the educational institution, which provide distinctiveness to school improvement plans (Tapia et al., 2020). The management capabilities of the head are an important factor when evaluating students, teachers, and other stakeholders' well-being. Thus, a student's outcome and academic success are greatly influenced by the type of school students have attended and the environment the school has to offer as a result of the sound management process adopted.

School Improvement Plan

Different stakeholders, including parents, learners, teachers, community members, and administrators, should participate in crafting the school improvement plan (SIP). These groups should be included in the development process as their opinions and suggestions can offer insightful information about what is successful and what requires improvement (Nelson, 2023).

School Improvement Plan (SIP) seeks to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the school and formulate solutions to solve the school's problems. The SIP is expected to make a lasting difference for change. It involves planning, a major process in which the school sets goals for improvement and makes a decision about how and when these goals will be achieved. The ultimate objective of the process is to improve the pupils'/students' performance level by enhancing the curriculum, improving physical facilities, and creating a positive environment that is more conducive to learning. Further, it also fosters and strengthens parents involvement in their children's learning home (Pacadaljen, 2021).

Methodology

This study used predictive-correlational research, a powerful tool for data gathering. This type of research provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behaviors of a particular population or subject. It is the common choice of researchers to gather information about a particular group or phenomenon. This study described the management process of school heads and school improvement plan outcomes. It also determined the significant differences and relationships among the said variables.

The study was conducted in 18 mega/big/central Public Elementary Schools in four divisions of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao Region, namely Maguindanao del Norte, Maguindanao del Sur, Cotabato City and Special Geographic Area Divisions. Based on Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) LIS/EBEIS 2023 records, here are the schools as following: Cotabato City Central Pilot School; Sero Central School; Notre Dame Village Central Elementary School; Vilo Central

Elementary School; L.R. Sebastian Elementary School; Parang Central Elementary School; Simuay Junction Central Elementary School; Broce Central Elementary School; Maguindanaon Elementary School; Sarmiento West Elementary School; Datu Unsay Central Elementary School; Kauran Elementary School; Tambunan Central Elementary School; Labulabu Elementary School; Datu Sangki Ampatuan Central Elementary School; Don Miguel Latada Elementary School; Endaila Silongan Central Elementary School and Simsiman Central Elementary School.

Moreover, the researcher selected only 281 respondents, consisting of school heads and teachers who were all currently teaching in the selected public schools, as part of the study's sample for the school year 2023-2024.

Furthermore, the respondents were chosen using the stratified sampling technique, which was done by classifying the respondents into subgroups from the 18 schools in the four divisions. Then, using Slovin's Formula, the sample size was computed from the total population, and only those available and accessible during the study were selected. Then, the proportional allocation was utilized.

The stratified sampling design is a probability sampling design that creates a stratum of the different subgroups under study.

Furthermore, the researcher used a self-made survey questionnaire formulated under the guidance of the research adviser. The survey questionnaire had two main parts. Part I asked about the extent of implementation of the management process adopted by the school heads. Part 2 consisted of statements about the extent of the School Improvement Plan outcome. The researcher used a four-point Likert scale that guided the respondents in selecting the extent of their choices in the given situations.

The processes of determining the validity and reliability of the instrument were done systematically. The instrument's validity was evaluated through the comments and suggestions of two professors from Cotabato State University and one external validator. The result revealed a mean of 4.57, which was interpreted as highly valid. On the other hand, the instrument's reliability was evaluated through a pilot test of 20 samples. Results were interpreted using Cronbach's Alpha method and analyzed and interpreted by the school research statistician. The result revealed a .985 rating, interpreted as highly reliable.

The weighted mean was used to describe the extent of the management process adopted by the school heads and the outcome of the school improvement plan. The Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient (Pearson r) determined the relationship between the school heads' management processes and the school improvement plan outcome. The Multiple Regressions Full/Enter Method was used to test which school heads' management processes best influenced the school improvement plan outcome.

Throughout the process, the researcher observed ethics in conducting this study. The researcher obtained informed consent from all respondents, including school heads and teachers, by clearly explaining the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits while assuring them of voluntary participation. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by coding response and securing data to prevent unauthorized access. To uphold the principle of non-maleficence, the researcher ensured that respondents are not exposed to harm, criticism, or professional risks. Additionally, the researcher prioritized beneficence by ensuring that the findings of this study contribute to improving school management practices and benefit educational stakeholders. Respondents were also informed of their right to withdraw at any time without consequences, ensuring that there is no coercion from school administrators. Moreover, the researcher upheld objectivity and integrity by avoiding biases in data collection and analysis while disclosing any potential conflicts of interest. Finally, the researcher secured ethical clearance from the appropriate institutional review board or ethics committee, adhering to national and institutional research ethics guidelines. By adhering to these ethical principles, the researcher ensured that the study maintains fairness, transparency, and credibility.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *The extent of the Management Process of the Schools Heads in terms of planning*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Invites the stakeholders to join in identifying the activities to be implemented.	3.25	Highly Practiced
2.	Gathers ideas from teachers to identify gaps in learning.	3.29	Highly Practiced
3.	Generates suggestions from parents on priority programs for students' instructional methods.	3.05	Practiced
4.	Leads the development of activities to be used to ensure instructional delivery efficiency.	3.20	Practiced
5.	Collaborates with partners on identifying support systems in the plans to be implemented.	3.16	Practiced
6.	Sits down together and plans for improvement of technology assets of the school.	3.01	Practiced
7.	Conducts collective planning with non-government agencies for resource building.	2.93	Practiced
8.	Invites local government officials to identify roles in education services.	3.05	Practiced
9.	Develops objectives to address identified school gaps and problems.	2.90	Practiced
10.	Conducts quarterly planning for strategies to enhance students learning.	3.11	Practiced
	Overall Mean	3.10	Practiced

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 1 presents the extent of the management process of the school heads in terms of planning, which got an overall mean of 3.10 interpreted as practiced. This result denotes that planning is part of the school's activity towards the improvement of service delivery. It reveals that different school partners do well-planned activities, such as setting objectives under the leadership of the school heads. This provides a wider scope of services and ideas that meet the needs of the school in quality service delivery.

According to Suyatno and Santosa (2022), planning is an integral part of activity design. Different agencies must participate in it to ensure no stone is left unturned. This can mean identifying what actions, such as resources and strategies, need to be formulated to meet the needs.

The answers revealed that the statement pertaining to the gathering of teachers' ideas in identifying gaps in learning that got the highest mean of 3.29 was interpreted as highly practiced. This result means presence and feedback from teachers are included in planning. Teachers, as the immediate contact of students, are vital aspects of planning; they are the ones who know the situations in the classroom.

Similarly, Panganiban (2018) explained that the approach of engaging teachers in planning improves the outcome. Teachers' contribution as students' representatives in identifying goals and designing learning activities can make a responsive outcome. Teachers know what the students need; therefore, their presence in program planning can identify those needs as part of the objective setting.

Although the development of objectives to address identified school gaps and problems got the lowest mean of 2.90, it is interpreted as practiced. This means that efforts are made to gather objectives from different sectors. Despite getting the lowest rating, it reflects that it is done. Identifying gaps first before setting objectives is good, for it can target the needed actions.

Sayyadi (2019) expressed the same idea, concluding that the ideal way to set objectives is through gap analysis. The gaps must be the basis for identifying the objectives of learning activities. This is a good way of formulating the target outcome of learning activities. A gap in learning requires immediate actions; thus, it must be part of planning the objectives.

Table 2. *The extent of the Management Process of the School Heads in terms of organizing*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Identifies officers in charge of programs to be implemented.	3.24	Practiced
2. Identifies the role of parents, teachers and other stakeholders in the program.	3.38	Highly Practiced
3. Provides authority to head teachers to design learning strategies for students.	3.28	Highly Practiced
4. Designs mechanisms to guide members of the team in instructional delivery.	2.95	Practiced
5. Allocates budget based on needs as prioritized by the team.	2.98	Practiced
6. Organizes student organizations to lead the students.	3.18	Practiced
7. Guides line agencies on support to be extended to the school.	2.72	Practiced
8. Assigns teacher to lead different programs implemented.	3.24	Practiced
9. Evaluates and assigns subjects based on teachers' competencies and qualifications.	3.00	Practiced
10. Facilitates strategies to meet school objectives.	3.01	Practiced
Overall Mean	3.10	Practiced

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 2 presents the extent of the management process of the school heads in terms of organizing, which got an overall mean of 3.10 interpreted as practiced. This means that the school heads are focused on harmonizing the plans towards attaining the objectives of the School Improvement Plan by ensuring resources and logistics are utilized as needed. Organizing is about using the different resources for the operation and service delivery of the school.

Sayyadi (2019) concluded that the ideal way to set objectives is through gap analysis. The gaps must be the basis for identifying the objectives of learning activities. This is a good way of formulating the target outcome of learning activities. Gaps in learning require immediate actions; thus, they must be part of planning the objectives.

The respondents gave the highest rating on the statement about identifying the role of parents, teachers, and other stakeholders in the program, with a mean of 3.38, which was interpreted as highly practiced. The result emphasizes collaborative contribution in ensuring service delivery is provided through harmonizing the different efforts. The act of helping each other to meet their learning needs can result in a blended operation and service. The importance of a parent's role, as well as that of stakeholders, is a vital aspect of resource development in schools. Parental and stakeholders' involvement in the education system is critical for many reasons. It has been shown that parental and stakeholder involvement helps with technical support as well as provides support for logistical needs. The assistance they provide can help the school provide the needed resources and services that the school alone cannot sustain (Dotterer, 2022).

On the other hand, the statement about the guidance to line agencies on support to be extended to the school that got the lowest mean of 2.72 was interpreted as practiced. This means that the school heads lead the different agencies in determining how they can extend their support. This can prevent duplication of services and ensure the assistance provided is the most needed resource or technical support.

According to Dooley (2022), stakeholders' support can improve community involvement by improving school-to-community communications. Stakeholders' involvement can also increase the support system and planning of the school. The impact of community and parental involvement on student achievement reveals a high correlation. This means it has made education services more helpful to the students.

Table 3 presents the extent of the school heads' management process in terms of controlling, which got an overall mean of 3.15 interpreted as practiced. The result shows that the school heads perform their duty, which is to monitor and evaluate the actual performance with the school's set standards to ensure that activities are performed according to the plans and, if not, then take corrective

action. This can provide proper guidance to the teachers in their directions.

Table 3. *The extent of the Management Process of the Heads in terms of Controlling*

Item	Mean	Interpretation
1. Checks teachers' compliance with curriculum designs.	3.41	Highly Practiced
2. Monitors students' progress in the outcome of the target activities.	3.20	Practiced
3. Supervises teachers in the utilization of instructional resources.	3.04	Practiced
4. Supervises the distribution of material resources for students' use.	3.27	Highly Practiced
5. Checks the available funding and procurement of resources for school operation.	3.07	Practiced
6. Monitors the pacing of lectures with curriculum design.	2.99	Practiced
7. Audits utilization of the school's operation budget.	2.98	Practiced
8. Observes teachers' performances in conducting learning sessions.	3.39	Highly Practiced
9. Instructs school staff to provide efficient services to the school.	3.27	Highly Practiced
10. Allocates resources based on the equitable needs of each staff and student.	2.88	Practiced
Overall Mean	3.15	Practiced

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Controlling is a systematic exercise that involves checking the actual progress or performance against the standards or plans to ensure adequate progress and recording any experience gained as a contribution to possible future needs. The exercise of school heads to control the school outcomes of school services is a good practice that can help attain the objectives (Bashin, 2023).

The answers show that the school heads check teachers' compliance with curriculum designs, with the highest mean of 3.41 interpreted as highly practiced. This result means the school heads are closely monitoring teachers' teaching methods. This can align instruction towards the curriculum guide being implemented by the department, helping in achieving the desired outcome.

The study by Burden (2020) explained that school heads' focus on teachers' compliance with the curriculum guide is absolutely vital. Teachers' performance is consistent towards educational achievement that can manifest significant contributions to students' higher learning outcomes. The presence of school heads in teachers' teaching performance is a good motivational driver for teachers' performance.

Meanwhile, the statement about allocating resources based on the equitable needs of each staff member and student got the lowest mean of 2.88 interpreted as practiced. This denotes that controlling resource utilization can help ensure that resources are wisely distributed. Schools may have limited resources; thus, allocating resources based on need is vital to providing the resources that are needed to meet the priority needs.

In the study of Cogtas (2018), controlling lessens resource wastage. This means that the school's resources are utilized properly. The needs will be the basis for the provision of materials and support to ensure learning needs and resources are provided with needed support to improve students' learning engagement.

Table 4. *The extent of the Management Process of the School Heads in terms of Activating*

Item	Mean	Interpretation
1. Rolls out programs designed to meet student learning needs.	3.19	Practiced
2. Implements the different programs indicated in the SIP based on timetables.	3.29	Highly Practiced
3. Observes the progress of students based on the objectives of the programs in the SIP.	3.15	Practiced
4. Checks the compliance of teachers in the activities to be implemented.	3.34	Highly Practiced
5. Provides reports on the progress of activities in the SIP.	3.26	Highly Practiced
6. Implements the child-friendly school program.	3.39	Highly Practiced
7. Engages parents in the implementation of PTA school projects.	3.26	Highly Practiced
8. Starts programs based on the timetable of the calendar of activities.	3.27	Highly Practiced
9. Uses Gantt charts to monitor the progress of learning programs.	2.93	Practiced
10. Involves teachers in carrying out instructional reform programs for students.	3.29	Highly Practiced
Overall Mean	3.24	Practiced

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 4 presents the extent of the school heads' management process in terms of activating, which got an overall mean of 3.24 interpreted as practiced. The result signifies that school heads ensure the on-time implementation of desired activities. The implementation of any project or activity will help achieve the outcome on time and can help provide the needed actions to help in learning outcomes.

One important aspect of the success of any plan is the activating phase. According to Piedde et al. (2019), the leadership of school heads in activating the programs and projects to commence on time is one way of attaining the objectives. The support of the school to start all plans on time will make the school services effective to the learners since school improvement plans were centered towards making education effective.

The respondents gave the highest rating to the implementation of child-friendly school programs, with a mean of 3.39, interpreted as highly practiced. This result denotes that the school gives the welfare of the children the highest priority in implementing its

improvement plan. The children's welfare can provide services that not only promote learning but also ensure the safety of children on the campus and in the community.

Similarly, Aquino et al. (2021) cited that one aspect of the plans of school service delivery is child-friendly services. This means offering activities that cultivate learning interests and protect the best interests of children. The provision of opportunities for learners to explore their ideas and to share with school activities can be one of the means to ensure they are given child-friendly services to increase their engagement. Child-friendly services yield quality assurance of attaining the outcome of school improvement plans.

On the other hand, the use of Gantt charts in monitoring the progress of learning programs got the lowest mean of 2.93, interpreted as practiced. This means that schools are also using a Gantt chart, which is a monitoring tool. However, due to modernization, other means of monitoring projects are used aside from the Gantt chart. This is helpful in determining the progress of target programs and activities.

This agrees with Gumus (2019), who cited that the use of Gantt charts can help visualize the building blocks of a project and organize it into smaller, more manageable tasks. The resulting small tasks are scheduled on the Gantt chart's timeline, along with dependencies between tasks, assignees, and milestones. Thus, in the setting of targets for School Improvement Plans it is useful to use a Gantt chart to guide all actors.

Table 5. *Management Process of the School Heads in terms of implementation*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Checks the roll-out of programs for students learning.	3.10	Practiced
2. Supervises the implementation of the inclusive education process.	3.02	Practiced
3. Ensures adoption of online learning for situations needed.	3.00	Practiced
4. Leads the implementation of students' reading programs.	3.21	Practiced
5. Spearheads the actual intervention of stakeholders in resource development.	3.05	Practiced
6. Guides the actual conduct of learning assessments in the class.	3.30	Highly Practiced
7. Supervises the implementation of technology use in instruction and learning sessions.	3.14	Practiced
8. Conducts intervention applications for students' learning gaps.	3.04	Practiced
9. Helps in the roll-out of infrastructure repair and maintenance.	3.12	Practiced
10. Leads the actual project implementation for a child-friendly school.	3.19	Practiced
Overall Mean	3.12	Practiced

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 5 reveals the extent of the management process of the school heads in terms of implementation got an overall mean of 3.12 interpreted as practiced. This means that school heads are directly involved in the conduct of the learning activities and programs for students. This implementation is a sign of action since it will translate the plans into action. This can bridge the objective and outcome to meet and achieve the desired result.

According to Otiento (2022), implementation is the execution or actions taken as part of the management process to ensure plans are attained. One effective measure of implementation is having a team leader lead the activities. This must be guided by the guidelines of the programs to be implemented. It must specify the resources needed and the time to start implementation.

The answers to the statement about guiding the actual conduct of learning assessments in the class got the highest mean of 3.30, which is interpreted as highly practiced. This result connotes that school heads are knowledgeable about the evaluations and assessments conducted by teachers to check students' progress. The implementation of the learning assessment set to the implemented curriculum can help monitor the students' and teachers' coping with it. This is the central aspect of learning development programs since improvement can be observed.

This agrees with Ozan and Kincal (2018), who emphasize learning assessment conduct. The management of principal on conduct of learning assessment translate messages to teachers that it must be done in accordance to the curriculum guidelines. The management and supervision of school heads of the implementation of assessment can put the program in place.

Nonetheless, the answer on ensuring the adoption of online learning for situations needed got the lowest mean of 3.00, interpreted as practiced. This result signifies that there are efforts to implement online learning; however, since there are limited resources, this has not yet been fully implemented. However, all schools are conducting orientation and using technology in their instructional systems. This can help upgrade the quality of education to be globally adopted.

Friedman and Friedman (2020) expressed the same view, emphasizing the urgency of implementing online learning. Online learning can augment face-to-face disruptions and make education services accessible to students. The management of school heads in implementing online learning can help identify challenges and initiate interventions.

Table 6 reveals the extent of the management process of the school heads in terms of monitoring, which got an overall mean of 3.25, which is interpreted as highly practiced. The result denotes that school heads regulate the monitoring activities for the performance of the teachers and students in the school improvement plans. The monitoring activities can identify the best practices and weak areas of school services. This can strengthen the implementation of the standards mandated by law.

The monitoring of the school head can serve as checks and balances of schools and their improvement as interdependent factors to

improve the services. Consequently, most monitoring authority objectives are to improve the quality of education in schools. This can identify the loopholes to improve the services (Prabowo et al., 2022).

Table 6. *The extent of the Management Process of the school heads in terms of monitoring*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Leads the assessment of learners' performance based on standards of curriculum.	3.15	Practiced
2.	Monitors the acquisition of resources for programs to improve the learning environment.	3.28	Highly Practiced
3.	Checks the teacher's compliance with the mandate to carry out school programs.	3.39	Highly Practiced
4.	Supervises the data gathering for the actual performance of programs implemented.	3.22	Practiced
5.	Checks the problems that hampers implementation of reading remedial class.	3.33	Highly Practiced
6.	Monitors the actual coping of teachers with the changes implemented in the school system.	3.11	Highly Practiced
7.	Observes the outcome of infusion of technology in school documentations.	3.30	Practiced
8.	Monitors the stakeholders' feedback on the school's compliance with agreements and programs.	3.27	Highly Practiced
9.	Checks the objective and time lime of the school improvement plans.	3.20	Practiced
10.	Monitors the capacities of implementers in relation to the school's financial status.	3.28	Highly Practiced
	Overall Mean	3.25	Highly Practiced

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

The answers to the question of checking the teacher's compliance with the mandate to carry out school programs got the highest mean of 3.39, which is interpreted as highly practised. This result shows the commitment of the school under the management of the school heads to follow and comply with the mandate of the government in the standardization of education. Through the monitoring of the school heads and how teachers comply, they can express an assurance that lectures are meeting the objectives of quality education. The school head can identify which areas the teachers need support, and she can augment this aspect.

A key aspect of meaningful monitoring is the willingness of all parties to give and receive focused feedback. The ultimate goal for a principal is to establish a culture in which staff are encouraged to reflect critically on their own practices and freely share their honest views on the implementation of school and district initiatives. Having the principal actively involved in such discussions benefits the overall school and enhances the principal's professional credibility (Bricker & Barclay, 2022).

On the other hand, the monitoring of the actual coping of teachers with the changes implemented in the school system got the lowest mean of 3.11, interpreted as practiced. This result shows that the school heads are concerned about how teachers adapt to change. The feedback they gather on the difficulties of teachers can help in providing solutions to ensure teachers can adapt and cope with the change, for it can directly affect the teaching process with students.

Monitoring and evaluation are both viewed as vital aspects of school program implementation to attain their goals. Monitoring is viewed as a process that provides information and ensures the management's use of such information to assess the coping mechanisms and effects of curriculum implementation by the teachers. This can help teachers feel they have somebody to lean on in times of difficulty, which can improve the difficult situations they encounter (Ford et al., 2019).

Table 7. *Extent of School Improvement Plan Outcome Achieved in terms of Improved Instructional Delivery*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Uses innovative teaching methods like technology-guided lectures.	3.18	Achieved
2.	Uses cooperative learning in class sessions.	3.38	Highly Achieved
3.	Adopts blended learning in instructional delivery.	3.41	Highly Achieved
4.	Integrates research-based instruction.	3.09	Achieved
5.	Adopts the learning differentiation strategies.	3.29	Highly Achieved
6.	Conducts scenario-based learning.	3.22	Achieved
7.	Localizes learning activities based on indigenous materials.	3.14	Achieved
8.	Adopts the principle of learning by allowing students to experience it.	3.39	Highly Achieved
9.	Uses age-appropriate learning materials.	3.32	Highly Achieved
10.	Uses simulation exercises to encourage students' participation.	3.40	Highly Achieved
	Overall Mean	3.28	Highly Achieved

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 7 presents the extent of the School Improvement Plan outcome achieved in terms of improved instructional delivery, which got an overall mean of 3.28, interpreted as highly achieved. This result shows that the school, through the programs under the School Improvement Plan, are able to carry out its mandate. This improved the delivery of instruction in innovative ways and helped learners to engage in education. The resources and the mode of instruction improved, resulting in improved student performance. The different instructional strategies helped in achieving the desired learning outcome for the students.

The success of an educational institution is based on the teachers' performance in instructional delivery, which is the way to achieve success by conveying education and ensuring that innovative strategies are implemented in instructional delivery under the guidance of the school heads. It is therefore important to make the management of school heads the foundation in instructional delivery as part of developing the quality of teachers to put the human capital into the productivity of the school in school outcome (Chandio et al.,

2021).

The respondents' answers reveal that the statement adopting blended learning in instructional delivery got the highest mean of 3.4,1, which is interpreted as highly achieved. This result signifies the full utilization of blended learning through modular and face-to-face with online learning in some schools. This can help teachers pursue the learning session during classes without face-to-face interaction. This is highly recommended for schools today as part of alternative learning modes.

This agrees with Durran (2019), who noted that efficiency and efficacy in an education context use blended learning as a transformational instrument for instructional delivery. Teachers' management and knowledge often depend completely on the coaching of their school heads. Teachers' performance and motivational approach to using blended learning can uplift the educational process and improve the quality of school services.

The teacher respondents answered that the integration of research-based instruction was achieved, with the lowest mean of 3.09 interpreted as achieved. This result shows that schools are using research results as the basis of planning for the improvement of school services. However, not all teachers are adept at conducting research, which sometimes becomes a hampering factor.

Many schools also experience this. According to Afdal and Damsa (2018) pointed that research-based instruction is part of developing a curriculum that makes it possible to prepare graduates who are able to address the challenges brought about by these developments, require a clear strategy with regard to new competencies, forms of knowledge and ways of working with knowledge. The edge of integrating research into instructional delivery is using a problem-based approach that can resolve learners' difficulties.

Table 8. *Extent of School Improvement Plan Outcome Achieved in terms of Instructional Resource Development*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Provides an adequate number of modules for students to use.	3.31	Highly Achieved
2. Distributes gadgets for students's learning support.	2.26	Less Achieved
3. Upgrades school technology equipment for ICT integration.	2.59	Achieved
4. Provides adequate books for students' references.	3.46	Highly Achieved
5. Uses visual aids in class activities.	3.56	Highly Achieved
6. Procures needed school learning materials like visual aids.	3.29	Highly Achieved
7. Constructs facilities like a library for students' reading time.	2.80	Achieved
8. Develops learning materials with localized dialect language.	3.27	Highly Achieved
9. Provides bulletin boards for the school's information drive.	3.01	Achieved
10. Provides Wi-Fi on the school campus.	2.76	Achieved
Overall Mean	3.03	Highly Achieved

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 8 presents the extent of the School Improvement Plan outcome achieved in terms of improved instructional resource development, which development got an overall mean of 3.0, as3 interpreted as achieved. This result means that through the use of the School Improvement Plan n, resources are provided and procured. The role of resources in the delivery of services is essential as it makes the instruction more interesting and attractive to the learners. Thus, learning improves.

For teaching and learning to be effective, instructional facilities and resources, which are the major supporting tools, need to be provided to the students. The lecturer uses these resources to deliver effective instruction. They aid lecturers in imparting helpful information to students. Instructional materials enhance the learner's comprehension of the lecture (Iyunade, 2021).

The respondents' answers reveal that the use of visual aids in class activities got the highest mean of 3.56, interpreted as highly achieved. This result means teachers are constantly using visual aids during learning sessions, which can be either face-to-face or online. The use of visual aids during lectures makes the students visualize the meaning of the words being discussed by teachers. This is useful in catching the interest of students and increasing their engagement.

In the study of Onasanya and Omosewo (2020), the adequacy of visual aids is defined as the availability of pictures and PowerPoint presentations during lectures. They explained that effective visual aids are helpful when the teaching tools used to teach a subject can meet the students' expectations regarding effectiveness and efficiency. To put it another way, the suitability of instructional materials like visual aids is determined by the ratio of the number of students to the available resources.

The respondents gave the lowest rating on the statement about the distribution of gadgets for students' learning support and got the lowest mean of 2.26, interpreted as less achieved. This result reflects the reality that many schools are still not yet equipped with technological equipment for students. The lack of budget to provide gadgets can make online classes not an alternative. This is supposed to be one of the best ways to increase students' interest in using technology to learn.

The presence of instructional materials like gadgets supports effective teaching and learning by letting the students participate in the activity. The use of gadgets in the present type of learners makes them interested in class discussions. But if it is not available, then it will make them feel let out and bored. One of the major problems of schools is the adequacy of gadgets for each of their students, for it is costly (Aliyu, 2019).

Table 9. *Extent of School Improvement Plan Outcome Achieved in terms of Students' Learning Development*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Increases completion rates of students.	3.15	Achieved
2.	Enhances literacy skills of students.	3.35	Highly Achieved
3.	Improves the critical thinking abilities of students.	3.27	Highly Achieved
4.	Develops self-regulation for students.	3.35	Highly Achieved
5.	Improves the reading and comprehension of students.	3.46	Highly Achieved
6.	Increases ability to solve mathematical problems.	3.31	Highly Achieved
7.	Widens vocabulary of students.	3.26	Highly Achieved
8.	Strengthens ability to comprehend situational analysis.	3.49	Highly Achieved
9.	Increases engagement in learning sessions.	3.48	Highly Achieved
10.	Ability to explain the topics presented by teachers.	3.46	Highly Achieved
	Overall Mean	3.36	Highly Achieved

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 (Highly Practiced) | 2.50 – 3.24 (Practiced) | 1.75 – 2.49 (Less Practiced) | 1.00 – 1.74 (Least Practiced)

Table 9 presents the extent of the School Improvement Plan outcome achieved in terms of students' learning development, which got an overall mean of 3.36, interpreted as highly Achieved. This result denotes that the school's management helps to ensure the implementation of the School Improvement Plan, which contributes to students' increasing learning achievements and meeting the goals of education. This made students develop the numeracy and literacy needed for a higher level of learning. This can prepare them for going to college or a future career.

According to Hou et al. (2019), the school's management of the learning activities makes the students learn the targeted competencies. This can increase their knowledge and skills and develop the right attitude as the objective of learning. The improvement in students' learning performance is manifested by literacy development passing rates and the use of this knowledge in day-to-day life.

The answers to the statement about strengthening the ability to comprehend situational analysis got the highest mean of 3.49, which is interpreted as highly achieved. This implies that through school heads' management of education programs, students were able to improve and acquire skills that will make them ready for the future. The improvement in comprehension can equip the students to become competitive, as this is basic to today's society.

Cahill et al. (2018) highlighted that the academic development of students is important in their daily lives; every day, they are developing and growing, especially their personalities as students. As students learn the basic knowledge of the concepts of the school, it provides them with competencies for a wider range of information that prepares them for the future, and as they grow, personalities are being developed and change towards becoming productive citizens, which are products of school mentoring them.

Among the answers, the statement about the increase in student completion rates got the lowest mean of 3.15, interpreted as achieved. This means that due to the effective management of school heads, students were able to finish their level and graduate. The completion rate reflects the accomplishment of the school towards its goal of ensuring students are educated and acquire education to prepare them for higher education or future lives. Though it got the lowest rating, it still means it has improved.

According to Duterte (2023), the target of the school improvement plan is to ensure increased completion rates of students. Low completion rates mean many students were not able to finish their education. Therefore, strategies to ensure no student is left behind must be sustained. Through increased completion rates, the school can measure its achievement in making education accessible to all.

Table 10. *Relationship between the Management Process of the School Heads and the School Improvement Plan Outcome*

<i>Management process of school heads</i>	<i>School improvement plan outcome</i>		
	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Planning	.69	.00	Significant
Organizing	.76	.00	Significant
Controlling	.83	.00	Significant
Activating	.78	.00	Significant
Implementation	.77	.00	Significant
Monitoring	.86	.00	Significant

** significant at .05 level of significance

Table 10 presents the correlation between the management process of school heads and the school improvement plan outcome using Pearson Product Moment. It was found that planning, $r=.70, p<.00$; organizing, $r=.76, p<.00$; controlling, $r=.83, p<.00$; activating, $r=.78, p<.00$; implementation, $r=.77, p<.00$ and monitoring $r=.86$ were all positively and strongly correlated with the school improvement plan outcome. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. The result confirms that the management planning of the school head contributed towards attaining the School Improvement Plan outcome that is centered towards improving the quality of education. This made the resources, teachers and learning environment utilized and provided to promote learning.

Similarly, the study of Gamala and Marpa (2022) emphasizes the impact of strong managerial skills in managing the various resources

in schools to achieve the mission of every school. School head management is also defined as a set of technical skills in facilitating and providing opportunities for teachers and resources through various activities to ensure the welfare of the students is given the highest priority.

Furthermore, school heads are seen as agents of change who contribute a major impression on the educational milieu through their management skills, creating supportive social connections, participating in mentoring programs, and fostering progress. Hence, through the management abilities of the school heads, school performance outcomes improved (Cherry et al., 2021).

Table 11. *Regression Analysis on the Influence of School Heads' Management Process in the School Improvement Plan Outcome*

Management Process of School Heads (Independent Variables)	School Improvement Plan Outcome (Dependent Variable)			
	Beta coefficient (β)	t	p-value (ρ)	Interpretation
Planning	.13	2.31	.02	Significant
Organizing	.14	1.66	.10	Not Significant
Controlling	.17	1.87	.06	Not Significant
Activating	-.12	-1.87	.06	Not Significant
Implementation	-.05	-.69	.49	Not Significant
Monitoring	.69	10.53	.00	Significant

R2 = .79; F = 170.66; df(6,276); $\rho < .00$
 Unstandardized B constant = .63; planning=.12; organizing=.12; controlling=.14; activating= -.16;
 implementation= -.42; monitoring=.63

Table 11 shows the multiple linear regression that was used to test which management process of school heads best influences the outcome of the school improvement plan. The overall regression (influence) was statistically significant, $R^2 = .69$, $F(6,276) = 170.66$, $\rho < .00$. It was further found that monitoring, $\beta = .85$, $\rho < .05$ best influence (Predictor) the school improvement plan output, followed by planning, $\beta = .13$, $\rho < .05$ while the rest of the variables has no significant influence on the dependent variable. This means that monitoring is an important aspect of the management process to ensure School Improvement Plans are attained. Through close monitoring, the progress of the learners and activities implemented are noted, and actions to meet the objectives can be taken.

According to Pulita et al. (2021), school heads' management abilities in monitoring the school system can contribute to the quality of education. It is understood that monitoring compliance with standardization and professionalism of the various components of the education system improves students' performance both academically and non-academically.

Conclusions

Based on the general findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

The extent of the school heads' management process in terms of planning got an overall mean of 3.10, organizing got an overall mean of 3.10, controlling got an overall mean of 3.15, activating got an overall mean of 3.24, and implementation got an overall mean of 3.12 are all interpreted as practiced. However, the monitoring got an overall mean of 3.25, interpreted as highly practiced.

The extent of the School Improvement Plan outcome achieved in terms of improved instructional delivery, which got an overall mean of 3.28, and students' learning development, which had an overall mean of 3.36, are both interpreted as highly achieved. However, the instructional resource development, which got an overall mean of 3.03, is interpreted as achieved.

The correlation between the management process of school heads and the school improvement plan outcome revealed that planning, $r = .70$, $\rho < .00$; organizing, $r = .76$, $\rho < .00$; controlling, $r = .83$, $\rho < .00$; activating, $r = .78$, $\rho < .00$; implementation, $r = .77$, $\rho < .00$; and monitoring, $r = .86$, $\rho < .00$ were all positively and strongly correlated with the school improvement plan outcome. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected.

The regression analysis of the management process of school heads best influences the outcome of the school improvement plan. The overall regression (influence) was statistically significant, $R^2 = .79$, $F(6,276) = 170.66$, $\rho < .00$

Based on the conclusions, it is recommended that the Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education may allocate funds for the improvement of the school's resources, particularly technology equipment. This can aid in the improvement of the learners' digital literacy skills. Moreover, the School Heads may organize informational sessions and orientations for teachers and stakeholders regarding the School Improvement Plan to make sure that everyone is aware of their roles in its execution. Moreover, the teachers may keep a close eye on the tactics in the school improvement plan so that they may apply them to their daily lessons with the learners. This may assist in achieving the objectives of the School Improvement Plan. Moreover, the stakeholders may provide school heads with technical support, such as workshops for their managerial development, as their role in guiding the institution toward higher overall performance is crucial. Lastly, to ensure that deserving but impoverished learners are not left behind in the digitalization of education, Local Government Officials may set aside funds to provide them with gadgets.

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